

Data Extraction Instrument

Blank instrument (data dictionary) — 72 prospectively defined fields

Project: Multimodal Artificial Intelligence for Acute Coronary Syndrome Detection: Protocol for a Systematic Review of Diagnostic Accuracy and Methodological Quality

Authors: Deepa Joshi, Lalit Garg, Joseph Cacciottolo (University of Malta)

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This is the blank extraction instrument accompanying the registered protocol. It contains no extracted study data.

Instrument architecture

The instrument is implemented as a single workbook of six linked tabs: (1) 1_Extraction holds, for every field, the extracted value together with a paired proof row; (2) 2_Evidence holds manuscript-facing evidence rows (funding source and conflict-of-interest statement, performance data used for meta-analysis, comparator validity note); (3) 2b_Conditional holds conditional housekeeping tags (e.g. mixed setting, inferred study design); (4) 3_RoB_Derivation holds the working for the seven derived risk-of-bias fields, each computed from its feeder columns by a fixed rule before the verdict is copied back; (5) Check supports internal verification; and (6) Backref logs backward-citation leads.

Proof-row convention. Each included study occupies two rows: a value row and a paired proof row (amber fill, Times New Roman 9 pt, wrapped) recording the page/location and a short verbatim quotation supporting every judgement-based value.

Calculated fields. Three fields are computed automatically and require no manual entry: PREVALENCE_PCT (Col 13), MODALITY_COUNT (Col 23), and ABLATION_DELTA (Col 52).

Derived fields. Seven fields (Cols 62–68) are not entered directly; they are derived on Tab 3_RoB_Derivation from their feeder columns and copied back. See the companion Risk of Bias Assessment Form.

Tokens for absent data: NR (not reported), NA (not applicable), None (explicitly reported as absent).

Field dictionary

Col #	Field name	Definition	Permitted values / format
Part 1 — Study identity and characteristics (Cols 1–12)			
1	PAPER_ID	Internal record identifier assigned at screening.	P01, P02, ... (free text)
2	AUTHOR_YEAR	First author surname and publication year.	Surname_YYYY
3	JOURNAL	Publishing journal or conference proceedings.	Free text
4	COUNTRY	Country/countries of the study population.	Free text
5	SETTING	Clinical setting of patient contact.	Prehospital / Emergency department / Chest pain unit / Inpatient ward / Catheterisation laboratory / Mixed
6	MULTICENTER	Whether data were drawn from more than one centre.	Yes / No / NR
7	STUDY_DESIGN	Observational design of the study.	Prospective cohort / Retrospective cohort / Registry-based / Cross-sectional

Col #	Field name	Definition	Permitted values / format
8	FUNDING_SOURCE	Primary funding category (detail + COI on Tab 2_Evidence).	Industry / Government / Academic / Mixed / None / NR
9	DATA_COLLECTION_WINDOW	Calendar period of data collection.	Free text (e.g. 2015–2019)
10	N_TOTAL	Total number of analysed units.	Integer
11	N_EVENTS	Number of confirmed ACS (positive) cases.	Integer
12	UNIT_OF_ANALYSIS	Unit on which the model operates / is evaluated.	Patient / Visit / ECG / Sample / Other
Part 2 — Outcome and modalities (Cols 13–24)			
13	PREVALENCE_PCT (auto)	Disease prevalence, auto-calculated.	Formula: = N_EVENTS / N_TOTAL × 100 (%)
14	INTENDED_USE	Stated clinical purpose of the model (tiebreaker field).	Triage-rule-out / Diagnosis / Decision-support
15	LABEL_SOURCE	Source of the outcome label used for training/evaluation.	Free text
16	OUTCOME_DEFINITION	Definition of the target outcome (ACS/STEMI/NSTEMI/UA).	Free text
17	REFERENCE_STANDARD	Reference standard used for adjudication.	4th UDMI / ICD + adjudication / Angiographic / Clinician diagnosis / Other
18	OUTCOME_BLIINDED	Whether outcome adjudication was blinded to model inputs.	Yes / No / NR
19	MOD_ECG	ECG signal data used as an input modality.	Yes / No
20	MOD_BIOMARKERS	Cardiac biomarkers used as an input modality.	Yes / No
21	MOD_IMAGING	Cardiac imaging used as an input modality.	Yes / No
22	MOD_OTHER	Structured clinical variables / other inputs used.	Yes / No
23	MODALITY_COUNT (auto)	Number of active input modalities, auto-calculated.	Formula: count of MOD_* flags = Yes
24	MODALITY_LIST	Explicit list of modalities entering the final model.	Free text
Part 3 — Model core (Cols 25–32) — extract in fixed order; tier first			
25	TIER_CATEGORY_TYPE	Integration-architecture tier (assigned first; governs EPV counting).	Tier A (representation-level / end-to-end) / Tier B (model-level learned fusion) / Tier C (feature-level concatenation) / Tier D (system-level non-learned)
26	EPV	Events per variable.	Numeric
27	FUSION_DESCRIPTION	How modalities are combined at the algorithmic level.	Free text
28	MODEL_TYPE	Primary model type (two-phase selection procedure).	Free text (e.g. logistic regression, GBM, CNN, transformer, ensemble)
29	MODEL_ARCHITECTURE	Architecture detail of the primary model.	Free text

Col #	Field name	Definition	Permitted values / format
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30	SAMPLE_SIZE_ADEQUACY	Sample-size/EPV adequacy (Riley et al. criteria).	Adequate / Inadequate / Unclear
31	MODEL_UPDATE	Whether an existing model was updated/recalibrated.	Yes / No / NR
32	PREDICTOR_TIMEPOINT	Timing of predictor collection relative to presentation (recorded last).	Triage-point / Post-serial-laboratory / Mixed / NR
Part 4 — Validation, performance, and comparators (Cols 33–53)			
33	VALIDATION_TYPE	Type of validation performed.	External-multi / External-single / Temporal / Internal-only
34	N_EXTERNAL_SITES	Number of independent external validation sites.	Integer
35	TEMPORAL_SPLIT	Whether a temporal train/test split was used.	Yes / No / NR
36	CV_METHOD	Cross-validation / resampling method.	Free text
37	AUC_INTERNAL	AUC/C-statistic on internal validation.	Numeric (0–1)
38	AUC_INTERNAL_CI_LOWER	Lower bound of internal AUC confidence interval.	Numeric / NR
39	AUC_INTERNAL_CI_UPPER	Upper bound of internal AUC confidence interval.	Numeric / NR
40	AUC_EXTERNAL	AUC/C-statistic on external validation.	Numeric (0–1) / NR
41	AUC_EXTERNAL_CI_LOWER	Lower bound of external AUC confidence interval.	Numeric / NR
42	AUC_EXTERNAL_CI_UPPER	Upper bound of external AUC confidence interval.	Numeric / NR
43	SENSITIVITY	Sensitivity at the author-defined threshold.	Numeric (%) / NR
44	SPECIFICITY	Specificity at the author-defined threshold.	Numeric (%) / NR
45	NPV_REPORTED	Whether negative predictive value is reported.	Yes / No
46	PPV_REPORTED	Whether positive predictive value is reported.	Yes / No
47	CALIBRATION_REPORTED	Whether any formal calibration metric is reported.	Yes / No
48	COMPARATOR_TYPE	Comparator against which the model is benchmarked.	Risk score / Unimodal AI / Standard care / Clinician / None
49	COMPARATOR_AUC	AUC of the comparator, where reported.	Numeric / NR / NA
50	ABLATION_UNIMODAL_AUC	Unimodal AUC in an ablation analysis.	Numeric / NR / NA
51	ABLATION_MULTIMODAL_AUC	Multimodal AUC in an ablation analysis.	Numeric / NR / NA
52	ABLATION_DELTA (auto)	Performance gain from multimodal integration, auto-calculated.	Formula: = ABLATION_MULTIMODAL_AUC – ABLATION_UNIMODAL_AUC
53	ABLATION_KEY_FINDING	Narrative of the ablation result.	Free text

Col #	Field name	Definition	Permitted values / format
Part 5 — Interpretability, deployment, methodology, RoB verdicts, audit trail (Cols 54–72)			
54	XAI_METHOD	Explainability method used (e.g. SHAP).	Free text / None
55	SUBGROUP_PERFORMANCE	Subgroup performance reported.	Free text / NR
56	FAIRNESS_ANALYSIS	Fairness / sex-stratified analysis reported.	Yes / No / NR
57	DEPLOYMENT_STATUS	Stage of clinical deployment.	Free text / NR
58	CODE_AVAILABLE	Whether model code is available.	Yes / No / NR
59	DATA_AVAILABLE	Whether underlying data are available.	Yes / No / NR
60	MISSING_DATA_METHOD	Handling of missing data (and timing vs split).	Free text / NR
61	CLASS_IMBALANCE_METHOD	Class-imbalance handling (and timing vs split).	Free text / None / NR
62	LEAKAGE_RISK [DERIVED]	Data-leakage risk; derived on Tab 3 (finalised after Cols 60/61).	None / Possible / Likely / NR
63	ROB_OVERALL [DERIVED]	Overall PROBAST+AI risk of bias; derived last from the four domains.	Low / Moderate / High
64	ROB_PARTICIPANTS [DERIVED]	PROBAST+AI participants domain; derived on Tab 3.	Low / High / Unclear
65	ROB_PREDICTORS [DERIVED]	PROBAST+AI predictors domain; derived on Tab 3.	Low / High / Unclear
66	ROB_OUTCOME [DERIVED]	PROBAST+AI outcome domain; derived on Tab 3.	Low / High / Unclear
67	ROB_ANALYSIS [DERIVED]	PROBAST+AI analysis domain; derived on Tab 3.	Low / High / Unclear
68	APPLICABILITY_CONCERN [DERIVED]	Applicability concern (separate axis); derived on Tab 3.	Low / High / Unclear
69	AUTHOR_CLAIM	Authors' headline performance claim.	Free text
70	AUTHOR_LIMITATION	Limitations acknowledged by the authors.	Free text
71	REVIEWER_NOTES	Audit trail; never left blank.	Free text
72	POSSIBLE_RELATED_REFERENCES	Backward-citation leads for the supplementary search.	Free text

Quality control. Two reviewers extract each study independently; disagreements are resolved by discussion, then by a third reviewer. Inter-rater agreement (Cohen's kappa) is computed on three fields — TIER_CATEGORY_TYPE (Col 25), ROB_OVERALL (Col 63), and LEAKAGE_RISK (Col 62) — on a random 20% sample; kappa < 0.60 on any field triggers a calibration session before extraction continues. Where a value in the text differs from a results table, the table value is used and the difference is logged in REVIEWER_NOTES.